
Leadership in Academic Library

Dr. S. R. Bodkurwar

Librarian, Shri. Gajanan Maharaj Mahavidyalaya, Mukutban,

Dist. Yavatmal. E.mail- shyamlib9@gmail.comatmal

Corresponding Author - Dr. S. R. Bodkurwar

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15559580

Abstract:

Libraries are knowledge of store house. It is also known as social agencies. Now day's libraries play a crucial role to the library and information center. Modern society has various needs such as education, research, cultural advancement information spiritual and ideological pursuits past time and recreation. Society have founded various institutions to serve these needs. As an effective human being, leader should have identity authenticity, open mildness, responsibility communicating, reasoning and problem-solving abilities concern for others, rest for life energy, maturing, courage, strong, sense of obligation, clarity of mind and expression, integrity etc. this article presently a roll of good leadership in the library and information center.

The paper describes the area of expertise, experiences skills associated with academic development positions in academic library and information center as basis for identifying leadership competencies that are relevant to academic library and administrator.

Libraries play a pivotal role in fostering knowledge and community engagement, yet the physical and mental well-being of both staff and patrons is often overlooked in their design and operation. This study explores ergonomic innovations in libraries, focusing on strategies to improve staff efficiency and enhance patron comfort. By integrating ergonomic principles into library furniture, workspace layouts, and technology interfaces, libraries can create environments that support productivity and accessibility.

Keyword: Leadership, Academic Library, Social agency, administrator, knowledge

Introduction:

Leadership involves various dimensions and attributes. It requires vision, courage, understanding determination, decisiveness, sense of timing, capacity to act, ability to inspire, etc. A leader is often judge by his mettle in a crisis. For example Winston Churchill during the London Blitz, John F Kennedy during the Cuban missile crisis, Indira Gandhi in the 1971 Bangladesh war, Margaret Thatcher during the miner's strike, Mikhail Gorbachev's break with communism and the cold war. In

these turning points, leadership made a crucial difference in modern history. It is the same in case of leadership in organizations

A person emerges as a leader and not appointed as a leader and there could be leaders of completely unorganized groups. A leader may not have a formal title or authority and he depends on his personal qualities and informal power to influence followers. There is always a mutuality of objectives between a leader and his followers but clash of objectives are likely between a manager and his

subordinates. Out of five basic sources of leadership power, namely, coercive power, reward power, legitimate power, expert power and referent power, the first three based on formal organization role are used by managers and the last two which are informal and individual oriented could also be used by leader.

A leader should have identity, authenticity, open mind ness, independence, responsibility, communicating, reasoning and problem solving abilities, concern for others rest for life energy, maturity, courage, strong sense of obligation, clarity of mind and expression , integrity, etc. Leadership is highly complex and elusive trait. Leadership is (often defined as the art of influencing others to strive willingly; to do what the leader wants them to do the mutually compatible objective) with zeal and confidence. It is encouraging and inspiring individuals and teams to give their best to achieve a desired result. Leaders work with and through people to accomplish goals. It is a psychological process of providing guidance for followers. Leadership is one of the most effective tools of management and organization effectiveness depends of the quality of leadership.

Function and Activity of Leadership:

Leadership implies and existence of followers, unequal distribution of authority among leaders and group members and commonality of interest between the leader and his followers. Further, leaders have to influence and direct their followers or subordinates. therefore, the main function of leadership is to include or persuade all subordinates Therefore, the main function of leadership is to induce or persuade all

subordinates or followers to contribute to organized goals in accordance with their maximum capability, Two major ingredients for skilled art of leadership are the ability to invent and use appropriate motivators and the ability to inspire. Fundamentals principles of leadership is “since people tend to follow those in whom they see a means of satisfying their own personal goals, the more a manager understands what motivates his subordinates and how those motivation operate, and more he reflects this understanding in carrying out his managerial action, and more effective as a leader he is likely to be” some of the common activity and function are mentioned below.

- **Goal setting:** A leader contributes significantly in establishing goals and objective of the organization.
- **Inspiring and Zeal building:** Appreciating the works of the subordinates, a leader inspires them to enthusiastically accept organization goals and contribute more towards goals.
- **Praising: Having** the interest of workers sincerely at heart a good leader past them for their good work.
- **Providing security:** A leader provide some sort of personal security to workers by maintaining a positive, optimistic attitude even in the face of adversaries
- **Representing:** A leader as a representative serve as a symbol of the organization and speaks for the organization, clarifies the organization position and hence compels outsiders to think of the whole organization in term of their

impression of the leader. In essence, he represents the organization.

- **Suggesting:** Suggesting often permits the subordinates to retain dignity and sense of participation.
- **Supplying objectives:** A leader defines and supplies objectives that will allow members to work together.
- **Bearing Group responsibility:** A leader act as a surrogate for individual responsibility of his or her subordinates.
- **Catalyzing:** Where some force is required to start or accelerate movement, a leader act as a catalyst and prods subordinates into action.
- **Executing:** As a manager, a leader not only contributes for planning but also takes responsibility for executing the plan.
- **Exemplifying:** A leader saves as a model for others to emulate and functions as an ideologist.
- **Expertise:** A leader is supposed to be an expert in the principal activities of the organization.

Leadership in Library and Information Center:

Based on the confidence of long practices, libraries were managed for long time with autocratic or paternalistic style. There was a general acceptance that power and authority rested naturally at the top of the library hierarchy. It is very much doubtful whether the same autocratic or paternalistic leadership style would be viable today. There has been steady and observed movement away from the autocratic, paternalistic, and hierarchical style of

leadership into an era of participation, consultation and delegation. The process of decision making is more widely spread through the organization than before. The external influences such as increased power of unions, economic pressures, labor and industrial relations legislation have substantially influenced managerial style. Even the general political climate is more hospitable to participation and consultation styles of management based on newer development in theories of human behavior and vehemently opposed to autocracy and authority. As a result “Hard orders are frequently displaced by acts of persuasion and suggestion; authority by influence and autocratic control by a participation matching of interest, skills ideas”

Good result and high performance were occasionally achieved by strictly adhering to orders and following direction from the top, but often such styles led to resentment from those who wished to make a large contribution to decision to decision making. While firmly directed, non-consultative methods are required from special occasions like crises, generally the planning and direction of library teams requires recognition of the value of member participation.” The situation in the modern library is such that expertise, creativity, intelligent and constructive thought and qualities of leadership can be found at all level”

Conclusion:

Management of libraries and information center in India is not only a very small subset of overall management in India in terms of leadership styles and managerial quality, but also a logical extension of

management of early libraries. The significant difference in managerial quality and leadership style of libraries. The significant difference in managerial quality and leadership styles of libraries and information center from that of the rest the stream could be traced to certain basic differences in the nature of libraries and information center themselves. Libraries, they are not profit service organization. Secondly, information center are of very recent origin. Thirdly, a very large proportion of librates and are supported from public fund. For these reasons, the style of management of information centers are more likely to be democratic and participative than gigantic Indian business house. Unfortunately, there is no worthwhile research in library and information science on these aspects to pin pointedly understand the situation

References:

1. Gopal, Krishnan (2006). *Leadership in Academic Library of the Present Century*, ILA Bulletin, 2006,42(3),13-17.
2. IGNOU Materials, MLIS 5, New Delhi
3. Khandawalla, Pradip N.(1992). *Organizational Designs for excellence*. New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill
4. Moore, Russell, F ed.(1970). *AMA Management Handbook*. New York: AMA
5. Tripathi, P C and Reddy, P N. (1991). *Principles of Management*. New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill